

Deliverable D-JRP21-WP1.23

Final Report JRP

JRP21-FBZ3.1-BIOPIGEE

Responsible Partner: BfR

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Title: Final Report BIOPIGEE

1. Consortium composition

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2. Summary of the work carried out in the Project

The OHEJP BIOPIGEE project aimed at identifying effective and cost-efficient biosecurity measures to control hepatitis E virus (HEV) and *Salmonella* occurrence in European pig farming. To achieve this, comprehensive literature reviews, field and experimental studies, expert opinion surveys and risk modelling have been used. The collated information was and continues to be disseminated to stakeholders (farmers, veterinarians, advisors) in illustrations, support tools and workshops.

During the field studies, farms and slaughterhouses were visited to look into the implementation of biosecurity measures and to take samples from pigs. The aim was to analyse associations between sample results and answers to questionnaires. For farms, a total of 264 questionnaires were received originating from nine European countries. A number of protective biosecurity measures could be identified. Additionally, data summaries were produced showing which biosecurity measures are used where at European pig farms. For slaughterhouses, the results from the questionnaire indicated that there were considerable differences between the slaughterhouses in implementation of best biosecurity practices throughout Europe. Although many biosecurity measures were in place, the results suggested areas of improvement. Either one should implement practices shown to be most effective (e.g. decontamination with hot water or steam vacuum treatment; bung sealing with plastic bag during evisceration; vertical scalding) or avoid practices shown to increase bacterial contamination of carcasses but are still used (e.g. pressure washing of carcasses at evisceration with cold water). The questionnaire was adjusted to be used as an assessment tool in European slaughterhouses.

During experimental studies the effectiveness of various disinfectants against the persistence of *Salmonella* in biofilms was studied and a HEV sampling method and infectivity test adapted for testing of HEVs in biofilm were developed. It was found that one needs at least 0.1% peracetic acid (PAA) for 10 minutes and at least 1% Glutaraldehyde (GA) for 30 minutes to successfully disinfect *Salmonella* in biofilm. For HEV, sampling with electrostatic dust collectors (EDCs) was studied. The developed sampling method is relatively easy to perform and can be executed in any laboratory without the need for sophisticated equipment. However further validation will be needed.

For modelling of the cost and effectiveness of biosecurity measures stochastic simulations on the effectiveness of biosecurity measures were performed and used to inform a cost-effectiveness analysis model. The results of this analysis suggested that, assuming a 100% implementation rate, anal bunging

at the slaughterhouse and organic acids in water or feed of weaner pigs on farm were the most cost-effective biosecurity measures for *Salmonella*, while none of the measures for HEV were considered cost-effective.

A literature review and meta-analysis to identify effective measures to control HEV, *Salmonella* and pathogenic *E. coli* in primary production had been performed. The measures were ranked according to their effect sizes in order to gain an impression of which measures might have the largest impact in practice.

Finally several online workshops were conducted with experts in the fields veterinary medicine, agriculture and meat industry in order to extract, inform about and discuss effectiveness of biosecurity measures and to rate country-specific biosecurity practices, as well as to exchange ideas on how to best disseminate the existent information and new information produced in BIOPIGEE.

Ideas about the content and presentation of material gathered in the BIOPIGEE project had been exchanged with a German farming education centre on how to set up the material to address farming pupils. This task is ongoing.

A guidance document is in preparation together with the publication of the findings taking into account the feedback received from stakeholders during the above-mentioned workshop.

Two tools have been developed. These are two checklist implemented as as interactive Excel-Spreadsheet. The checklists are based on the benchmark system developed in the project. One checklist addresses the control of *Salmonella* on pig farms, the other deals with the control of HEV on pig farms.

Given the topics of the project and its outcomes, it may have the largest impact for ESFA. The outcomes include guidance for farmers, veterinarians, consultants and slaughterhouses in European countries in form of illustrative flyers and web content to inform stakeholders, incl. collaborating farm education centers. The material should provide reliable and cost-efficient guidance on the reduction of *Sallmonella* and HEV spread in animals and humans (through occupational exposure) which add important information for monitoring and regulation in order to advance One Health.

3. Work carried out in the JRP/JIP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

Note: In the following the running years of the project correspond to the running years of the OHEJP. That means that the first year of BIOPIGEE is 2020, which is the third year of the OHEJP. Therefore, the first year of BIOPIGEE is designated as “Y3” (i.e. year three of OHEJP). Correspondingly “Y4” and “Y5” correspond to the second and third year of BIOPIGEE.

WP1 Project coordination and integration of results

WP1-T1 Project management and meeting organisation

Y3 : The BIOPIGEE Kick-off meeting was organised and successfully conducted at BfR in Berlin/Germany on 29th-30th of January 2020. All participating organisations were represented, of these 41 BIOPIGEE members took part. Four quartely WP leader meetings were organised and held. The BIOPIGEE OHEJP website had been filled with content, participants were invited to join. All general, important and finalised documents had been uploaded to the page and status updates had been written. Shared documents had been set up and updated versions uploaded to the BfR cloud server. Links and passwords to open these documents were stored at the BIOPIGEE website. Thereby, data protection as well as access of only project people was ensured. Production of a BIOPIGEE flyer in WP6/ OHEJP Communication Team was supported with text modules and images.

Y4 : The BIOPIGEE Mid-term meeting took place - virtually due to the pandemic - on 2nd/3rd March

2021 (organised with APHA) where all WPs and Tasks presented their work, results, challenges and further plans which were discussed with the group. Four quarterly WP leader meetings and collaborations with other projects and institutions were arranged. An online glossary of relevant terms in BIOPIGEE had been developed between task groups in cooperation with the MATRIX project. Since several tasks of the project had been affected by the pandemic situation (farm visits, lab work, workshops), changes in the timeline of tasks and consequences for links between Tasks/WPs were coordinated. The Gantt chart and the list of due dates for deliverables and milestones were modified accordingly. In agreement with all project partners, despite budgetary consequences, a 6-month-extension of the project was requested (April '21) in order to enable fulfilment of planned tasks. The work plans of all WPs for Y5, 2022, had been modified together with WP-leaders taking a 6 months extension into consideration.

WP1-T1-ST1 Definition of biosecurity measure

A new subtask “Definition of ‘biosecurity measure’ across WPs/Tasks in BIOPIGEE” (WP1-T1-ST1- was later moved to WP5, as Task T0) was identified and initiated.

Y5 : Four quarterly meetings of the WP leaders had been arranged and held to discuss current issues. A collaboration with the HealthyLivestock project is ongoing and project outcomes had been exchanged and discussed, e.g. in workshop events. Some tasks are still being affected by the pandemic (farm visits, lab work, workshops) and changes in the schedule and organisation of tasks and consequences for links between Tasks/WPs had been coordinated. The Gantt Chart and the list of due dates for deliverables and milestones had been modified accordingly. The BIOPIGEE online glossary was updated and supplemented with the definition for “biosecurity measure” after its publication. The final meeting was organized by IZSAM (IT) and BfR (DE) and then successfully held in presence in Guilianova Italy on 6 and 7 October 2022. From 10 countries attended 36 participants of which 8 were participating online. Most participants were from the 14 partner institutions of the project. Two participants were invited, one from EFSA and one from CEVA (NL).

WP1-T2 Development of data management plan

Y3 : First, the elaboration of the data management plan was started. All WP-leaders were invited to fill the “old” xls-sheet regarding their data. Later, we were informed that the former tool DMPonline will not be supported by OHEJP any further and a search for a better tool is under way. The deadline for the first version of the DMP was delayed by the OHEJP-PMT. Hence, work on the DMP was put on hold until September 2020. Introduction to the new tool CDP for the DMP took place on September 9th 2020. Afterwards, we filled the DMP in CDP and are waiting for further instructions from OHEJP-PMT (was announced for January 2021).

Y4 : A draft of the data management plan (DMP) was developed with WP leaders and entered into the CDP-tool in 2020. From the CDP-tool, an excel sheet of the DMP was downloaded, uploaded to the BIOPIGEE website and transferred to a shared document hosted at the BfR-server. Updates made by WP leaders in the shared document in June, August, October and December 2021 were transferred to CDP.

New options to describe complex data in the DMP have become available as was informed in a training session by the DMP group in March 2021. In addition, contact information, keywords, description and file types were updated for each piece of data listed in the BIOPIGEE DMP as suggested by DMP group during 2021. The DMP will be updated repeatedly until the end of the project.

The DMP includes currently 21 different kinds of data, which are closely related to deliverables of the project. It is research data and methodologies, mainly related to pigs as focused in the project. Most of the data are intended to be published in scientific journals and are therefore confidential until

publication. Location, where to find the data (e.g. website, Zenodo) is listed together with information whom to contact for each dataset (names, institutions and email addresses), which have a unique identifier in the plan. There is little to consider for ethical aspects as data will be anonymised and no personal or identifiable data will be included. Data related keywords from ORION were selected on a drop down list in the CDP tool and are also used in the BIOPIGEE DMP. Thereby, the DMP takes into account the following aspects: data summary, making data findable, making data openly accessible, making data interoperable, increase data re-use (FAIR data principles), data dissemination, data security and ethical aspects.

Y5 : The data management plan was revised according to comments by the OHEJP WP4 DMP group at the beginning of 2022 and had been updated continuously both in a shared document in the project group and in the Lisam CDP tool. With the end of the project, the BIOPIGEE DMP comprises the description of 35 data items.

WP1-T3 Provision of project deliverables and reports

Y3 : First deliverables (questionnaire, flyer, data management plan, HEV infectivity assay) and the 9M report had been provided, via the private group and/or Zenodo.

Y4 : The publication plan for the project, arranged in a shared document, was modified to indicate the status of publications (intended, in work, submitted, accepted, published) for WP2 to WP5 and had been continuously managed. Here also references and links of finalised publications have been collated. Deliverables were continuously collected and distributed (uploaded to the private web-group and to Zenodo). Reporting was a repeated task. The annual work plan (AWP) for Y5 was amended together with the WP leaders, considering a 6-months-extension and was submitted to OHEJP coordination team (9th June 2021) and silently accepted (without any comments) by the OHEJP coordination. The 9M-report 2021 and the 12M report 2021 were prepared together with the WP leaders and delivered.

Y5 : The publication plan for the project, compiled in a shared document, had been modified to inform and exchange information about the status of publications and had been continuously managed. Deliverables had been continuously collected, checked and distributed (uploaded to the private web-group, to Zenodo and forwarded to OHEJP WP3/CommsTeam). The 9M report and the final report had been delivered.

WP2 Biosecurity effectiveness studies.

WP2-T1 Development of biosecurity protocol

Y3 : A biosecurity protocol for European pig farms was developed in order to assess the relevance of measures on the prevalence of Salmonella and hepatitis E virus. As first step, existing protocols from Europe and North America were assessed but, on evaluation, it was decided to design a new protocol specific to the needs of the project. Evidence from a literature review and expert opinions (scientists) was used to inform the content of this protocol. The biosecurity measures were reworded as questions (55 biosecurity questions for indoor, 56 for outdoor situation), and questions on general farm characteristics (10) and economic/performance factors were added.

WP2-T1-ST1 Transfer of the questionnaire into an electronic version

The questionnaire was transferred into an electronic survey tool and translated into the necessary languages of the countries participating in WP2-T2. An app for this survey was produced, set up on devices of interviewers in each of the participating countries and the

function of the app and data transfer to a central server were tested, with support of WP1. This system enabled standardized data collection, and facilitated data income and evaluation.

WP2-T2 Application of the biosecurity protocol

Y3 : The developed biosecurity questionnaire was applied on pig farms in the participating countries. Farms were recruited and 59 farm visits took place in nine different countries. Incoming survey data had been reported to the interviewers quarterly to check and prepare for later data evaluation. Pictures were taken of examples of good biosecurity practice, to add to the project documentation in work package 6.

The task was delayed due to different restrictions in EU member states related to worldwide pandemic of coronavirus disease COVID-19. NL decided not to collect fecal samples that they had planned in this task for *Salmonella* testing but instead will attempt to use results from routine meat juice sample surveillance to identify high and low risk farms. There were difficulties in all countries to visit farms and to take sample as initially planned. Although most countries started farm visits in autumn 2020, these continued to be disrupted by COVID-19 lockdowns, as well as African Swine Fever concerns, restricting access to farms and the willingness of farmers to allow access. Biosecurity data from 90 pig farms from a previous ANSES study was collected and aligned to questions within the biosecurity protocol to allow their usage in this study.

The sampling, laboratory testing and recruitment protocols were designed. Details of the HEV-testing methods were discussed between partner labs and participants of WP2-2 and WP2-T5 in order to harmonise methods as much as possible and to reach comparability of results that can also supplement the HEVnet database.

Y4 : Although COVID-19 restrictions had a large impact on the progress of the task, as of 1st December 2021, all of the planned farm visits (264) had taken place. Corresponding questionnaires had been uploaded onto the electronic data capture system from nine countries (DE, NL, CZ, PL, BG, UK, AT, IT, EE) with additional data provided by two other countries (SE and FR). Almost 4,000 samples were collected from field visits and tested for *Salmonella* and hepatitis E virus (HEV). NL and EE used data from national *Salmonella* monitoring, or other sources of information, to help categorise their farms as being at higher or lower risk for these pathogens. Analysis had been completed to determine the significant associations between biosecurity measures and the risk category of each pathogen. Pictures were taken during farm visits to show case examples of good and bad biosecurity practice, to add to project documentation in work package 6.

Y5 : The analysis of the biosecurity questionnaire and HEV/*Salmonella* laboratory results was completed. Descriptive analysis of the data was carried out, with particular focus on presenting differences in biosecurity measures between farm types and participating countries/ regions. Multivariable risk factor analysis and principal component analysis have been completed to identify the most effective biosecurity measures in controlling *Salmonella* on European pig farms. These results have been shared with WP4 and WP5, so that cost-benefit analysis can be applied to the identified measures and the benchmark system can include the measures. To assess the potential effect of bias on the task 2 results, a number of sensitivity analyses were also completed, which confirmed the suitability of the multivariable risk factor model. Similar analyses have been completed for HEV . Publications are being drafted from these analyses. Additionally, a biosecurity dataset from the Republic of Ireland is being shared with the project team to allow a paper to be produced on the use of biosecurity on pig farms on almost 400 European farms in 11 countries.

WP2-T3 Slaughterhouse biosecurity practices

Y3 : This Task was planned to start at the beginning of Y4 but already started this year to collect existing national and local assessment protocols on biosecurity measures in slaughterhouses. A first virtual meeting took place in September 2020.

Y4 : An online survey was designed to collect information on best biosecurity practice in slaughterhouses. The survey took place in seven countries (DE, CZ, EE, IT, AT, UK and NL) with 32 responses. The survey included 20 questions organised into the sections general, transportation, lairage (waiting area at the slaughterhouse where arriving pigs are kept until slaughter), scalding, singeing, evisceration, carcass splitter, decontamination and chilling. The content was based on information about biosecurity measures' effectiveness presented in peer-reviewed literature and on opinions from slaughterhouse experts within the partner institutes.

Sampling methods for visits to slaughterhouses were agreed within the team. Bacteriological samples were collected from three slaughterhouses, one in CZ and two in IT. The samples were collected along the slaughter line to help validate information on the effectiveness of biosecurity practices. The evidence from the studies had been collated into a report on the effectiveness of slaughterhouse biosecurity.

Y5 : The results from the slaughterhouse literature review, sampling visits and questionnaire survey that were collected from this study are being organised for two publications.

WP2-T4 Field studies

Y3 : The study plans for the three proposed studies were designed and the teams were in contact to assess synergies and harmonisation of techniques to improve comparison of potential findings. The overarching protocol was uploaded to the BIOPIGEE page and was thereby made accessible to the whole consortium.

Y4 : This task was largely affected by COVID-19 lockdowns in the participating countries. However, longitudinal studies were started in the UK. In NL, the research focus for this task was updated and refocused on internal biosecurity and spread of HEV between pens. A pilot study on four farms was completed, the results of which were analysed and informed the final study protocol (choice of farm and age groups to sample) for the longitudinal study. Unfortunately, recruitment in NL was delayed due to farmers withdrawing participation or being found to be HEV negative.

Y5 : In the UK, two longitudinal studies were completed to investigate the epidemiology of HEV, in particular with regards to the mixing of pigs and potential environmental reservoirs. The first trial was a two-stage breeder-finisher unit, and the second trial was a weaner-finisher unit, and both were visited four times to collect samples from a cohort of pigs, from entry onto the farm through to slaughter. The results suggested a wide range of environmental reservoirs and that earlier mixing of pigs effected the timing of the peak of prevalence in the cohort group.

In the Netherlands, two longitudinal field studies were carried out investigating the transmission rate of HEV between consecutive batches of finisher pigs in the same pens, and between pens within compartments. A secondary aim was to investigate whether PRRS pre- or co-infection influences the latent period, or the duration of infectious period of HEV in a pen of finisher pigs. Every pen was faecal sampled once a week, and serum samples were collected at the beginning and end of every batch to identify contingent HEV infection prior to the fattening stage, and seroconversion during the fattening phase. Between batches, pens were sampled post cleaning and disinfection. In the first farm, all pens were HEV negative, although boot socks of the first batch were positive in the last week prior to slaughter, demonstrating that HEV was still present on the farm and transmission was possible. On the other farm, all pens became positive, and the moment of infection in a pen was dependent on the compartment the pen is in, and presence of a positive adjacent pen. As the study is linked to a separate

project, data collection is continuing beyond the end of the BIOPIGEE project and will be thoroughly analysed during the next year.

In Italy, ten farms were recruited for a study which aims to determine the effectiveness of cleaning and disinfection procedures on farms against *Salmonella* and HEV. *Enterobacteriaceae* were also enumerated to have an indication of residual faecal contamination. The study did not investigate individual cleaning regimens or disinfectant products. Samples were taken on four farms in April 2022. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic and the recent African Swine Fever outbreak in Italy it was not possible to recruit finisher farms as initially proposed, and therefore farrow-to-wean and weaning farms were recruited instead. Each farm was visited before and after cleaning and disinfection. All samples collected were negative for *Salmonella* and HEV; however, *Enterobacteriaceae* colony count ranged from negative to 105 cfu/cm² (mL) and indicated suboptimal cleaning and disinfection in some of pens.

Three publications are planned to present the findings from these studies.

WP2-T5 Analysis of HEV prevalence and subtypes

Y5 : 266 HEV sequences from BIOPIGEE samples from seven countries were uploaded onto the HEVnet website along with relevant metadata on farm types, country of origin and biosecurity measures associated with HEV in WP2-T2. These have been used for sequence diversity analysis and assessments of association with diversity. The results will be presented in a publication.

WP3 Impact of disinfection on persistence of pathogens in biofilm

WP3-T1 Comparison of methods for testing the effect of disinfectants

Y3 : Discussion about and planning of methods and reference strains to be used by all participating laboratories had taken place.

Y4 : Parameters to compare methods for testing disinfectants effectivity were described. Reference strains to be used by all participating laboratories had been defined. Biofilm methods between labs had been compared. Methods to continue with in Task 2-ST2 had been defined. The deliverable WP3.7 “Assessed methods for testing disinfectants on *Salmonella* in biofilm” was produced and submitted in August 2021.

Y5 : This task had been finalized for using reference strains. Additional data are being produced using wildtype strains.

WP3-T2 Effect of disinfectants on biofilm-associated wild type *Salmonella*

Y3 : Method establishment started.

WP3-T2-ST1: Selection of wild type *Salmonella* isolates

Discussions about choice of the panel of *Salmonella* isolates, and finalisation of the method to be used to screen the isolates for biofilm forming abilities had taken place.

WP3-T2-ST2 Assessing the effect of disinfectants

Labwork started with initial testing.

Y4 : Disinfectants and conditions and biofilm methods to be used had been defined. Wild type strains had been selected and sent to all participating laboratories.

WP3-T2-ST1: Selection of wild type Salmonella isolates

A panel of Salmonella isolated from UK pig farms had been screened for their biofilm abilities using two methodologies. From this panel, six biofilm-forming Salmonella isolates, from serovars Derby and Typhimurium, had been selected for the use in Task WP3-T2-ST2.

WP3-T2-ST2 Assessing the effect of disinfectants

Each lab used the already locally established biofilm model for testing the effectiveness of disinfectants. Lab work started with initial testing.

Y5 : The panel on wildtype strains had been selected and shared with all partners. Disinfectant efficacy testing had been done.

WP3-T2-ST2 Assessing the effect of disinfectants

The panel on wildtype strains had been selected and shared with all partners. Disinfectant efficacy testing had been finalized. The efficacy of two disinfectants (Glutaraldehyde and Peracetic acid) at various concentrations had been studied. The assessments were performed using three different biofilm models on wild- type strains selected in the previous sub-task.

Deliverable 3.19 had been submitted.

A Poster had been presented at Eurobiofilms 2022 (31.8.22-3.9.22, Mallorca, Spain) and a manuscript is in preparation.

WP3-T3 Study of HEV stability in relation to disinfection approaches

Y3 : Preparations were made to study the HEV stability in microfilms using appropriate HEV infectivity assays which partly had been developed in WP3-T3-ST1, and had been further implemented in Y4 (and Y5).

WP3-T3-ST1 Implementation of HEV infectivity assay for testing biofilms

A first version of the HEV infectivity assay had been completed. In this assay primary hepatocytes are isolated from liver tissue of (HEV free) piglets using a collagenase treatment. The obtained primary hepatocytes are aliquoted and stored at -180 Celsius until use. For the actual assay the hepatocytes are seeded onto plates and inoculated with different concentrations of HEV. First HEV replication plots had been established.

A second option for testing of HEV infectivity, precision-cut liver slices (PCLS) had been used. PCLS cuts had been directly transferred to an ice-cold organ preservation solution and inoculated with different concentrations of HEV and tested daily using qRT-PCR for increasing levels of HEV RNA. Single replication rounds had been observed but the method still needs optimisation.

Y4 : HEV stability in microfilms had been be studied using appropriate HEV infectivity assays which had been developed in WP3-T3-ST1, and had been further implemented in Y4 (and Y5).

WP3-T3-ST1 Adaptation and implementation of HEV infectivity assay for testing biofilms

The HEV infectivity assay was completed. In this assay, primary hepatocytes are isolated from

liver tissue of (HEV free) piglets using a collagenase treatment. The obtained primary hepatocytes are aliquoted and stored at -180°C until use. For the actual assay, the hepatocytes are seeded onto plates and inoculated with different samples potentially contaminated with HEV. A second method for testing of HEV infectivity, precision-cut liver slices (PCLS) had been developed and had been used further for validation of the hepatocytes assay. Adaptations of the bioassay had been made in order to make it suitable for testing biofilms.

The deliverable WP3.6 “HEV infectivity assay is available” had been implemented further. It had been tested on field samples and had been further validated using other HEV bioassays.

The deliverable WP3.5 “Method for testing persistence of infectious HEV in surface microlayers” was completed.

The deliverable WP3.20 “HEV infectivity test adapted for testing of HEV in biofilms” was completed.

WP3-T3-ST2 HEV in Salmonella biofilms

We investigated whether there was a correlation between the presence of HEV and Salmonella in faecal samples of pigs. No significant correlation had been seen, however more samples need to be tested to obtain reliable outcomes. The method how to sample the environment/biofilms had been developed and tested. Electrostatic Dust Collectors (EDC) had been used to swab the environment/ biofilm. The virus had been eluted, which means adsorbed material was removed from the adsorbent, EDC, by means of a solvent (5ml of cell culture medium in this case) and tested for the presence of HEV with the use of real time PCR. In case of a positive result the sample will be grown in the HEV infectivity assay.

Y5 : Work on sub-taks ST2 and ST3 has been concluded.

WP3-T3-ST2 HEV in Salmonella biofilms

The deliverable WP3.14 “Information on the persistence of infectious HEV in surface microlayer/biofilm” had been submitted.

WP3-T3-ST3 Field study of HEV and Salmonella co-occurrence at pig farms

On two different pig farms, environmental samples (291) were collected after the cleaning procedure. Samples were analysed for the presence of HEV and Salmonella in order to study if HEV may be more stable in Salmonella biofilms. Using electrostatic dust collectors, floors, walls, feed bowls and drink nipples were sampled. The wipes were processed in PBS and DNA and RNA were isolated using the pathogens kit of Zymo research. Isolates were tested for HEV and Salmonella by real-time PCR. In 171 out of the 291 samples, Salmonella DNA was detected (Ct between 29 and 38). In 15 out of the 291 samples, HEV RNA was detected of which 10 positives were in Salmonella positive samples and 5 positives in Salmonella negative samples. It was concluded that there was no significant correlation between the presence of Salmonella and HEV. An in-vitro study on Salmonella biofilms combined with an experimental HEV infection will not be conducted as this will have no added value.

WP4 Modelling of the cost and effectiveness of biosecurity measures

Summary

In WP4 we developed models to simulate the transmission of HEV and Salmonella along the pig production chain and assessed the effectiveness of various biosecurity measures. These models were used to inform a cost-effectiveness analysis. The results suggested Anal bunting at the slaughterhouse and Organic acids in water or feed of weaner pigs on farm were the most cost-effective biosecurity measures for *Salmonella*, while none of the measures for HEV were considered cost-effective. In future, it might be worth considering the cost-effectiveness against multiple pathogens or whether targeting biosecurity measures to high-risk farms might improve the cost-effectiveness.

To simulate the transmission of HEV between farms and the prevalence in pigs sent to slaughter, a model combining complex network analysis and exponential random graph models was produced (Hammami, P. *et. al.* 2022). This model confirmed the topological stability of the network over time while highlighting the important roles of companies, types of farm, farm sizes, outdoor housing systems and batch-rearing systems. This model also investigated the effectiveness of some on-farm biosecurity measures, but found that the only factor that looked like it would have a big effect was a hypothetical measure that would reduce the prevalence of a concurrent immunomodulating virus.

This slaughter pig prevalence from the network model acted as an input to a quantitative microbiological risk assessment (QMRA) for the slaughter to consumption phases of the pig production chain, which included modules to simulate human exposure via minced meat, liver pate and sliced liver (Wilkins, N., 2022). The QMRA output was an estimate of human HEV infection with and without biosecurity measures implemented, which informed the cost-effectiveness model. This model estimated that while HEV RNA is likely to be present in all products, only the sliced liver was likely to have sufficient infectious virus to cause human illness. For Salmonella, a pre-existing QMRA was used to simulate the impact of various biosecurity measures on human cases, to inform the cost-effectiveness analysis.

The cost-effectiveness model weighed the benefits of the estimated reduction of human cases and reduced pig prevalence against the cost of a 100% implementation rate of the biosecurity measure. Monetary values were ascribed to human salmonellosis/HEV cases by cost of illness analysis. Previously published values on the animal health impact due to *Salmonella* were assigned to pig cases. Unfortunately, lack of data did not allow the evaluation of the economic animal health impact due to HEV within the time frame of the project (see more on this and other issues encountered in WP in Section 4). Costs associated to the implementation of a biosecurity measure were evaluated measure-specific and, if data allowed it, country-specific. The cost-effectiveness model was applied to the year 2019.

WP4-T1 Development of questionnaire on biosecurity costs

Y3 : A questionnaire with respect to health and performance data of pigs located in farms was developed which covers 24 questions. The questionnaire was delivered to the partners of WP2-T1, who used it during their empirical survey at the farm level. Questions about the costs of biosecurity were not included. The reason is that the costs of the selected biosecurity measures will be difficult and very time-consuming to answer for the farmers. Thus, the costs of the biosecurity measures will be estimated using usual country prices such as disinfection costs per litter and via monetary values from the scientific literature. This concluded WP4-T1.

WP4-T2 Stochastic simulations on the effectiveness of biosecurity measures

Y3 : Three online meetings were held to coordinate and harmonise the different tasks of 4.2 and 4.3 between the partners. In these meetings the adaption of currently available transmission models such as QMRA for Salmonella and SimInF model for HEV and/or Salmonella of the consortium partners had been discussed in order to analyse the impact of biosecurity and other mitigation measures (e.g. at the

slaughterhouse) on prevalence reduction of the zoonotic pathogens. During the meetings, In- and Outputs of the models were discussed. Furthermore the data requirements for the planned transmission model were discussed. This included e.g. the type of transmission data, meta-data on the animal population like movements data of pigs, and necessary data inputs of the other WPs 2, 3 and 5 about the effectiveness of biosecurity measures and/or mitigation measures on the reduction of prevalence values.

WP4-T2-ST1 Data collection for the transmission models

Data requirements for the transmission model was discussed between the partners as well as the outputs of the single models considering different type and aggregation of input data from the other WPs. Additionally, the data requirements and their availability were discussed. The R codes of the available models were presented to each member involved in WP4. The latter procedure was necessary so that everyone has the same level of knowledge about the inner workings of the R codes and associated strength and limitation of the corresponding transmission models.

WP4-T2-ST2 Adaption of the models based on the available data

The simulation model is had been planned to run for three countries for which all data needed are available. The adoption of the models started e.g. incorporation of the effect of biosecurity measures on the spread within and between herds in the R Code.

Y4 :

WP4-T2-ST1 Data collection for the transmission models

The data collection phase for the network model was completed, but there were issues with obtaining pig movement data for some of the proposed case study countries. Data were obtained and successfully integrated into the model from France. Data were obtained from the UK, but due to data privacy issues, some data (e.g. information to identify individual farms) could not be shared. Considerable effort was put in to developing methods to allow geographical data to be used instead, but unfortunately this did not leave enough funding to fully integrate the UK data into the model and validate the results. The method is developed to allow this in the future, but the resource is unlikely to be available within BIOPIGEE. It was not possible to obtain movement data from Italy and while a potential source for similar data from Germany was identified, it was not possible to obtain the data in time.

Data collection for the QMRA continued and a number of potential gaps had been identified, particularly in relation to inactivation rates and dose-response for HEV, which we will look to resolve over the next year of the project.

Y5 : The baseline QMRA for HEV and *Salmonella* had been completed and validated. The models had been run for multiple biosecurity intervention measures. Some measures had been parametrised using prior data from published literature and some using the results of the longitudinal studies conducted in WP2. Unfortunately, due to data and resource issues it had not been possible to run the models for multiple countries, but this would be feasible in the future if sufficient data become available. This WP collaborated the colleagues developing the economic model in WP4-T4, to ensure the model outputs WP4-T2 were appropriate to act as inputs to the model in WP4-T4. For each measure, the output metric of probability of human illness was calculated. This was then compared against the baseline run to determine the effectiveness of the measure. Comparing the effectiveness between individual biosecurity measures allowed identifying which measures the model predicts to be most effective. These outputs then acted as inputs to the economic model. Deliverable WP4.17 was submitted.

WP4-T3 Merge of models into one QMRA

Y3 : Work just started at end of Y3.

Y4 :

WP4-T3-ST1 Different transmission models will be matched to one QMRA zoonotic pathogen model

Draft results of the farm-to-slaughter network transmission model with the French data had been produced, including simulations of some on-farm biosecurity interventions. This work is currently in publication process.

Despite delays due to staff resourcing, COVID-19 and outbreak response work related to avian influenza, work had done to adapt the previous Salmonella QMRA for HEV. This included developing methodology for consumption of liver as a route of human HEV infection and a methodology to simulate the inactivation of HEV during cooking of liver. Data collection had identified a number of potential gaps, particularly in relation to cross-contamination rates at the slaughterhouse, inactivation rates and dose-response for HEV.

Discussions had taken place to ensure successful integration of the network model with the QMRA at the slaughterhouse stage. A poster on this process had been presented at the 2021 OHEJP annual meeting.

Y5 : The outputs of the French network model developed by ANSES had been provided as inputs to the QMRA. This allowed for a full farm-to-consumption analysis to be done for these input data. Unfortunately, due to resource, data and logistic issues it was not possible to fully connect the models developed by different countries into one fully functional model. In particular, it proved problematic to obtain pig movement data and impossible to obtain permission to share that raw data with multiple countries in the time available for this project. As such, future use of the full model would rely on the individual institutes running their own sections.

WP4-T4 Economic model of biosecurity measures across Europe

Y4 : Work on this task had not started until M46 as the initial task leader, Beate Pinior/Conrady, left the project. A new member, Clara Bester took over this task in M47. Initial work concentrated on analysing the cost-related data collected within WP2 Task2 during the farm visits in several countries. Furthermore, a concept for the cost-benefit analysis had been developed taking into account outcomes from a literature review conducted within the COHESIVE project.

Y5 : Data from selected example countries had been collected for conducting the economic analysis by applying the concept of a Cost Benefit Analysis (CBA). Biosecurity measures for the analyses based on the results from WP2-T2 and WP5-T2 had been selected in communication with BIOPIGEE team members from WP4-T2 and WP4-T3. The selected biosecurity measures had been individually evaluated by using the pathogen specific QMRAs. Unfortunately, due to technical and logistical issues, only one measure had been considered at a time. Costs for the selected biosecurity measures had been identified based on the initial definition of the measure in the original study from the literature, which evaluated the effect of the measure as well as consulting national guidelines and expert opinions. Additionally, cost-of-illness analysis were conducted for human salmonellosis cases as well as human HEV cases.

WP5 Benchmark of biosecurity practice

WP5-T0 Definition of biosecurity measure

Y3 – Y5:The new task “Definition of biosecurity measure” was moved from WP1 to WP5. The group developed a common understanding of ‘biosecurity measure’ across project tasks based on applied

inclusion/exclusion criteria from five BIOPIGEE task groups and a literature scoping review including four scientific databases. The definition proposal was presented at the ONE-Health, Environment, society-2022 conference, and at BIOPIGEE online workshops. An article manuscript presenting and discussing the definition in detail has been published in 2022.

WP5-T1 Data integration from WP2-4 in catalogue of biosecurity measures

Y3 : With support of WP1, an online table (“BIOPIGEE: Biosecurity measures Salmonella and HEV”) was set up starting the WP5 catalogue of effective biosecurity measures for HEV and Salmonella prevalence. Data from WP2 to WP5, especially from a brief review in WP2-T1, were integrated into the catalogue. All BIOPIGEE participants were invited to supplement the BIOPIGEE catalogue of biosecurity measures. The catalogue had been updated continuously with identified biosecurity measures and estimates of their effectiveness. At the end of the project, this catalogue should represent a valuable resource for the project’s stakeholders working on food safety and the reduction of Salmonella and HEV in pork products.

Y4 : The catalogue of biosecurity measures to reduce HEV and/or Salmonella prevalence was revised to consider all relevant data from the project, to ensure consistent data and safe updates. Procedures for inputs and updates as well as backups were defined. Data was updated by the first results from WP5-T2 and WP5-T4. All BIOPIGEE participants were invited to supplement the BIOPIGEE catalogue of biosecurity measures. The catalogue had been updated continuously with identified biosecurity measures and estimates of their effectiveness.

Y5 : The BIOPIGEE catalogue of identified biosecurity measures had been filled with findings on effective measures to control HEV and *Salmonella* occurrence at different production stages in primary production and at slaughter as well as on expert opinion. This task lost the leader. The project leader asked task leaders to add their results to the catalogue organised in a shared document.

WP5-T2 Literature review/meta-analysis

Y3 : A systematic literature review about the effectiveness of biosecurity measures specifically against Salmonella and HEV in pigs farms had been nearly finished. The search question, terms, period, and in- and exclusion criteria had been defined in the group with the help of a shared online document. The articles found in literature databases had been evaluated and the extraction of the relevant data is expected to be finished in M36. Afterwards the data will be categorised and prepared for the meta-analysis. The meta-analyses will be performed for all biosecurity measures for which sufficient studies were published in order to estimate their effectiveness to reduce Salmonella- and HEV-prevalence in pig herds. As additional data, e.g. about the way of pathogen detection, productions stages and farm types, were extracted from the literature, stratified meta-analyses might be possible which will provide more targeted effect estimates. Besides providing information for the catalogue of biosecurity measures (WP5-T1), the results of this task will be used in WP4 to parametrise the simulation models. Although it won’t be possible to offer first estimates to WP4 at the end of M36, the data processing and meta-analyses had been done in close consultation with WP4 to support WP4 in defining dummy variables for the simulation based on preliminary results until estimates will be available. Thus, WP4 can advance in coding and testing their simulations and the time lost due to the delay in task WP5-T2 had been minimised.

This task had been delayed because some partners, who contributed intensively, were additionally charged with COVID-19 related tasks and had to leave the work group. This had been solved on a higher level, but delays occurred due shortage of personnel for 4 months at BfR after the initial project lead had left. Besides, technical issues around conference tools strained communication between partners until solutions had been found. Thanks to personnel reinforcement at BfR since November this task had been finalised with the help of the group, but with some delay. The task was anyway planned to

be carried out in steps and to run until 2022.

In the review, we concentrated particularly on biosecurity measures included in the questionnaire in WP2-T1 and for which no references on proving evidence of effectiveness had been identified in WP2-T1. Therefore, knowledge gaps in information from WP2-T1 had been analysed.

Y4 : A first round of a systematic literature review about the effectiveness of biosecurity measures specifically against *Salmonella* and HEV in pigs farms had been finished with the help of 10 reviewers from 7 countries, who evaluated about 1650 articles found in literature databases and according to a harmonised scheme. Relevant data were extracted and estimates of the effectiveness of the identified biosecurity measures were summarised by meta-analyses. The risk of bias of the included articles was assessed. First effect estimates were offered to WP4 at the end of M38 and entered in the catalogue of biosecurity measures (WP5-T1).

In a second round the systematic literature and meta-analyses was then updated and expanded, including biosecurity measures to reduce the occurrence of pathogenic *E. coli* in pig herds. In this round, a total of 11 reviewers overall participated from 7 different countries. Tutorials on literature screening, data extraction and risk of bias analysis were held to instruct participants. In this updating turn, a software-based machine learning tool, ASReview was applied alongside the manual screening by reviewers, with thanks to the collaboration from the University of Utrecht. In total for the manual screening, 5130 article titles were initially included and 1185 abstracts were screened in duplicate. For ASReview, 4068 articles were uploaded onto the software and 536 abstracts were screened. After further full text screening, 82 articles moved to data extraction and finally risk of bias analysis, with a final sample of 54 papers deemed to have sufficient primary data to be extracted for the analysis. Data cleaning of the extracted estimates had continued by four partners throughout December and January. Work had been delayed due to a lack of staff at BfR and elsewhere to conduct the analysis of the extracted effect estimates.

Y5 : The literature review and meta-analysis to identify effective measures to control HEV, *Salmonella* and pathogenic *E. coli* in primary production had been finalised in a joint work between 6 partner countries/institutes. Finally, 35 articles met the inclusion criteria (4 on HEV, 29 on *Salmonella*, 2 on pathogenic *E. coli*). From these articles, 14 observations on measures related to HEV, 145 related to *Salmonella* and three related to pathogenic *E. coli* control were extracted. Most measures addressed biosecurity categories like Cleaning & Disinfection (42), Mixing of pigs (35) and FeedWaterBedding (24). The results were transferred to the biosecurity catalogue (WP5-T1).

A manuscript is currently being drafted to present the study and its results intended to be published in a scientific journal.

WP5-T3 Machine learning approaches

Y3 : This task had not started yet. However, it had been discussed to drop or change it in order to support the data analysis / imputation of missing values in task WP2-T2 because that task might need additional time and/or finish the data acquisition with much less data than planned due to the COVID-19 -restrictions.

Y4 : This task had not started yet and conduction is unclear as the task leader left the project and replacement is unclear. Partly, the additional use of ASReview replaced this task.

Y5 : The prediction of effectiveness of specific biosecurity measures with the help of a machine learning approach and to inform the biosecurity catalogue appeared not useful anymore and had therefore been cancelled. Instead, we used the ASReview tool in WP5-T2 to automate and complement part of the comprehensive and thereby labour- and staff intensive literature review on global biosecurity practice.

WP5-T4 Expert panel to add estimations on effectiveness/ weights

Y3 : This task will build on and expand the expert panel set up and surveyed in WP2-T1 (scientists) to additionally incorporate knowledge of other stakeholders like practitioners, advisors, etc.. A list of types of experts to recruit had been compiled. A comprehensive discussion had taken place about which kinds of experts to invite and how to categorise them. This fruitful discussion showed that there are marked differences between the veterinary and consulting systems within the pig sectors of the different partner states. These differences in the systems considerably influence the understanding of the roles within the pig sector of different professions. A shared spreadsheet with predefined types of experts was created and a first selection of experts from several countries agreed to support the panel. Further experts had been contacted. The procedure of the expert interviews had started to be defined and the expert survey had been prepared. For this, the questions from the questionnaire of WP2-T2 needs to be reworded to statements and any possible need for translations had been identified between partners. Scoring categories for evaluating the responses of experts had been discussed and developed.

Y4 : The questionnaire about biosecurity measures in primary pig production, developed in WP2-T1 and applied on farms in WP2-T2, was adapted for an expert survey to assess the importance of biosecurity measures to reduce Salmonella and HEV occurrence in different pig production systems.

For this, questions were reworded to best practice statements, considering results from WP5-T2 literature review, and the initial expert panel from WP2-T1 (scientists) was expanded to additionally incorporate knowledge of other stakeholders like practitioners, advisors, etc.. We finally identified and agreed on the grouping of expertise and then recruited representatives from participating countries for the panel. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the interviews were carried out with an online questionnaire.

The experts were asked to:

- 1) Rate their own expertise for the pathogens HEV and Salmonella, for the husbandry systems and for biosecurity;
- 2) Select the setting(s) they wanted to answer questions for (settings: HEV*indoor keeping, HEV*outdoor keeping, Salmonella*indoor keeping, Salmonella*outdoor keeping);
- 3) Rank the effectiveness of eight biosecurity measure categories, scoring them between 1-80 based on their importance for pathogen prevention/control, and
- 4) within each category, score each specific measure, based on its relevance to control within each setting, between 1 (least relevant) and 5 (most relevant).

Responses from 46 experts (from PL, UK, DE, BG, AT, IT, SE, NL, BE, EE, NO) could be included in the analysis. The experts' answers to the questionnaire had been analysed.

Results indicated that, no biosecurity category stood out, with all category contributing to some extent. The experts confirmed the high importance of the majority of the biosecurity measures within the categories, nonetheless activities related to animal movement/mixing as well as cleaning/disinfection practices were consistently ranked high for all settings. Additionally, gaps relating to outdoor farming and HEV in pigs were identified and should be targeted in future research.

A manuscript for this study is intended to be submitted to a scientific journal.

Y5 : A manuscript for the study on biosecurity measures prioritised by experts to control HEV and *Salmonella* in indoor and outdoor pig production has been prepared between authors from six countries and has been submitted to Porcine Health Management.

WP5-T5 Benchmark system for effectiveness of biosecurity practice

Y5 : This task started in M51. Task group meetings took place (1-2 per month). The list of participants, the objective and subtasks were clarified and organised. At first, effective biosecurity measures were collated based on incoming data from the other tasks WP2-T2, WP5-T2, WP5-T4 (collected in the WP5-T1 catalogue). Only measure that met the BIOPIGEE definition of biosecurity measures (clarified in the additional BIOPIGEE task WP1-T1-ST1/WP5-T0) and which proved to be effective (based on former studies or on results from WP2-T2) were included in the benchmark list. The wording of the measures was prepared in agreement with reference information, task partners and in consultation with WP4-T4. The measures were grouped as in WP2, WP4 and WP5 and ordered by prioritisation of experts (panel). A benchmark system had been developed which addressed different production stages and pathogens. A traffic light system had been used and cut-offs were found in applying the benchmark checklist to example farms from WP2-T2 with the help of the collected survey data.

WP6 Dissemination

WP6-T1 Assembly and development of biosecurity information

Y3 : Collection of best biosecurity illustrations (pictures) during farm visits of WP2-T2 had been described in the Sampling protocol of WP2-T2. The task had been delayed due to the COVID-19 outbreak as farms could not be visited by some partners with subsequent delays in collection of illustrations.

WP6-T1-ST1 Identification of appropriate websites or other online channels

A shared file at the BIOPIGEE website had been developed to list appropriate channels for dissemination in partner countries. Twenty-one web sites in six countries had been identified for dissemination.

WP6-T1-ST2b Provision of slaughterhouse protocol to slaughter industry/related associations

The start of this task had been postponed from M31 to M43 when effective biosecurity measures for slaughterhouses had been analysed in WP2-T3.

Y4 :

WP6-T1-ST1- Identification of appropriate websites or other online channels

The list of web sites for dissemination had been revised and the original 21 web sites across six countries had been kept. The shared document had been made accessible to all partners via a link on the OHEJP BIOPIGEE website.

WP6-T1-ST2a Provision of information for farming schools and websites

Illustrations of examples for good biosecurity (pictures), to be used in this task, were collected in WP2. Pictures from different partner countries' farms had been assembled and uploaded to the OHEJP BIOPIGEE website. Ideas about the content of this material had been exchanged with an advisory service in Germany as well as at the online workshop between the BIOPIGEE project group and the T5.4 expert panel.

WP6-T1-ST2b Provision of slaughterhouse protocol to slaughter industry/related associations

A slaughterhouse biosecurity protocol/questionnaire has been developed and sent to slaughterhouses in seven countries (DE, CZ, EE, IT, AT, UK and NL).

The deliverable WP6.15 “Biosecurity protocol on slaughterhouse provided” had been completed in December 2021.

Y5 :

WP6-T1-ST1- Identification of appropriate websites or other online channels

The list of web sites for dissemination had been revised and the original 21 web sites across six countries was kept.

WP6-T1-ST2a Provision of information for farming schools and websites

The material in the form of leaflets for farming schools consisting of information on the project itself, best biosecurity practices with pictures as illustrations had been prepared for dissemination by BIOPIGEE partners. Ideas about the content and presentation of this material had been exchanged with a German farming education centre on how to set up the material to address farming pupils.

WP6-T1-ST2b Provision of slaughterhouse protocol to slaughter industry/related associations

An online workshop on findings about effective biosecurity measures to control *Salmonella* (and HEV) at slaughter of pigs was held on September 16th, 2022. A guidance document is in preparation together with the publication of the findings taking into account the feedback received from stakeholders during the above-mentioned workshop.

WP6-T2 A support tool for calculating cost effectiveness

Y5 : A tool had been implemented based on results from WP4-T4. It calculates an estimation of the cost-efficiency of biosecurity measures along the food chain.

The calculation tool is created in Excel, to allow users an easy access and evaluation of costs and benefits of selected biosecurity measures. The measures were identified through a literature review and meta-analysis conducted in WP5-T2. Results are searchable for four countries (Austria, France, Germany and United Kingdom). In WP4-T4 the cost-benefit analysis was conducted based on the comparison of an estimated current implementation rate of a biosecurity measure (WP2) against an assumed 100% application rate within a country. The figures incorporated into the calculation tool are the output from this cost-benefit analysis. All currently available results from WP4-T4 have been transferred into the calculation tool. The tool design allows additional data to be added at a later stage.

A prototype of the tool is established. After finalizing the output-design, the tool will be distributed via the BIOPIGEE website and the corresponding deliverable report.

WP6-T3 Organisation of a workshop-series

As a preliminary remark it must be stressed that plans for the workshop series had to be altered due

to the COVID-19 pandemic. Instead of arranging the workshops in conjunction with relevant conferences, the first workshop was cancelled and replaced with smaller national or regional events for disseminating information on the project and to gather input from stakeholders. Stakeholders to invite had been identified for the expert panel (WP5)) and WP6 (workshops). The physical workshops were replaced with three online workshops. The first was held on 14 December 2021 to which the expert panel was invited and discussed preliminary results from the BIOPIGEE project and provided input for work during the final year of the project. The second and third workshops were held on 14 and 16 September 2022. These two workshops targeted different audiences as the the second workshop adressed primary production while the third addressed biosecurity during slaughter. The latter two workshops were well attended with more than 100 registered participant per workshop.

Y3 :

WP6-T3-ST1 Identification of relevant experts

WP5 and WP6 together identified relevant experts and stakeholders to invite to the expert panel and workshop series, respectively. Interested parties were listed at the BIOPIGEE website.

WP6-T3-ST2 Identification of relevant conferences

Relevant conferences were listed in our publication plan (link to shared document at BIOPIGEE website had been provided) and recurrently revised. However, no workshops could be carried out in conjunction with a conference because of the pandemic and after lifting restrictions due to the pandemic, reluctance from the organising committee of the ESPHM conference to enable this. The ESPHM conference had been identified as the best option for the workshop as it attracts pig practitioners and the scientific community related to porcine health management, the timing in May 2022 and the location in Budapest, Hungary.

WP6-T3-ST3 Organisation of Workshop 1

The fist workshop was cancelled due to the COVID-19 pandemic and replaced with regional or national events which has been carried out in Germany.

Y4 :

WP6-T3-ST1 Identification of relevant stakeholders

BIOPIGEE partners revised the list of stakeholders ifentified For the second workshop, an expert panel, recruited for T5.4, was invited for a web-meeting to discuss BIOPIGEE results. National contact BIOPIGEE partners sent out the invitation to a total of 84 identified experts in eleven countries.

WP6-T3-ST2 Identification of relevant conferences

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, physical conferences were cancelled. Relevant conferences for hosting the third workshop in 2022 in conjunction with a conference, were listed in our publication list, options were discussed in the WP leader meeting in June and September 2021. The ESPHM was identified as a suitable conference for hosting a pre-congress workshop arranged by the BIOPIGEE consortium . The discussion continued in the beginning of 2022 but the plan was dropped as the ESPHM board did not allow for a pre-congress symposium at a suitable time preceding the conference despite .quite far-reaching plans for a hybrid event.

WP6-T3-ST3 Organisation of Workshop 1

Due to the Covid pandemic, the first workshop was cancelled. National information events are planned instead. In Germany, participation in information days of and with animal health services took place to inform and discuss results from BIOPIGEE (25th Nov 2021). Here, contacts and exchange with a German consultancy service for biosecurity practice in pig farming and with a German training centre for farming apprenticeship were initiated. This exchange may be beneficial with testing and giving feedback when designing the information material in WP6-T1-ST2a and the support tool in WP6-T2.

WP6-T3-ST4 Organisation of Workshop 2

An online workshop was held on 14th December 2021. Listed experts for WP5-T4 were invited to this half-day-workshop where preliminary results from the BIOPIGEE project were presented and discussed. There were in total 62 participants from 11 countries, 35 project members and 27 externals. The panel was represented by 17 participants.

The presentations gave a good overview about first findings. Main points in the discussions were how we define and delimit biosecurity measures in pig production and what has been so far learned about transmission of HEV between pigs. Moreover, a focus of this workshop was the exchange of ideas about how and where to disseminate outcome of the project to spread knowledge on best biosecurity practice in pig production.

Y5 :

WP6-T3-ST1 Identification of relevant stakeholders

For the workshops, stakeholder groups had previously been identified. These were invited by:

- 1) main contact persons at the partner institutes per country,
- 2) the OHEJP CommsTeam, and by
- 3) Task WP2-T3 (slaughterhouse panel).

WP6-T3-ST5 Organisation of final Workshops

The first onsite workshop at the beginning of the project was replaced by national dissemination events where findings and feedback could be exchanged. The events are described in the deliverable D-JRP21-WP6.3.

After one online workshop at which project findings were discussed with the WP5-T4 expert panel in December 2021 (deliverable D-JRP21-WP6.10), another two virtual workshops were planned for the end of the project. These two workshops were held in mid of September 2022; instead of one onsite workshop. The goal of the two workshops was to present and discuss findings on effective biosecurity measures in

- 1) primary production and
- 2) at slaughter,

each targeting a particular and still wide audience of stakeholders. The workshop for primary production (deliverable D-JRP21-WP6.26) included outcomes from WP2-T2 and WP2-T4 field studies, WP4-T4 economic modelling, WP5-T2 literature study and WP5-T4 expert survey. The second workshop (deliverable D-JRP21-WP6.28) addressed literature information and a

guidance document on effective slaughterhouse measures and sample results from slaughterhouses in CZ and IT (outcome from Task WP2-T3). In both workshops the implementation of effective measures in respective operations have been discussed.

WP6-T4 Production of BIOPIGEE flyer

Y3 : WP6 (supported by WP1 and the OHEJP Communication Team) produced a BIOPIGEE flyer with brief information material about the project for handing out to farmers (WP2-T2), to external collaboration partners, at conferences, at workshops (WP6-T3) and when recruiting experts for the panel (WP5-T4).

WP6-T5 Press release

Y4 : A press release about activities in the project has been drafted between partners (DE, UK, AT, SE) and published at the beginning of 2021.

WP6-T6 Glossary of terms used in BIOPIGEE

Y4 :A glossary of terms used in BIOPIGEE has been developed between tasks and is hosted in the infrastructure of the OHEJP MATRIX project. The BIOPIGEE Glossary can be accessed via a link on the OHEJP BIOPIGEE website since 17th December 2021. In 2022, the definition of “biosecurity measure” was published and afterwards it was added to the glossary.

4. Project self-assessment

According to the proposal plan, effective biosecurity measures for the control of both Salmonella and HEV occurrence in the pig production (food) chain had been identified in the project and also disseminated to stakeholders.

In WP2, delays were encountered in recruiting and visiting farms, due to the COVID-19 pandemic and African Swine Fever presence in participating countries. The extension of the overall project helped us recruit close to the expected number of farms. Additionally, farm data was sourced from other studies as a backup plan and these will be used for an additional publication. The delays still impacted upon the ability to produce analytical results to inform the other workpackages in good time, which impacted slightly upon their use of the data. However, the WP managed to achieve all its aim and produced novel and robust datasets for epidemiological analysis.

WP4 encountered issues around sharing of sensitive pig movement data between countries, as such it was only possible to run the network model for France in the time available. This highlights a major issue around data availability across countries which hampers the development of models with EU wide applicability. In future, consideration could be given as to whether models could be shared rather than the data. For Salmonella, we were able to produce results for Austria and the UK, giving us results for three countries overall, but not the countries suggested in the original proposal.

Another issue in WP4 identified was the difficulty in obtaining relevant outputs from the longitudinal studies. This issue was only identified at a late stage of the project, future studies should allow for earlier communication between WPs regarding the type and format of data outputs expected and data inputs required. These issues meant that, while results for multiple biosecurity measures identified in the other WPs were produced, for both HEV and Salmonella, we were unable to produce results for all of them.

Also in WP4 it was found that very little data were available to parameterise the HEV QMRA in terms of actual infectious virus, which is the relevant microbiological variable for predicting the probability of infection and hence the expected number of human cases. As there were significantly more data available concerning RNA copies, a methodology was developed which relied on 'conversion factors' between RNA copies and infectious virus. The nature of these conversion factors was subject to high uncertainty, hence this approach resulted in high uncertainty around the number of human cases. However, the human exposure, i.e. levels of HEV RNA consumed, and the relative difference in HEV cases between biosecurity measure were considered more robust.

Finally, WP4 encountered issues due to three other problems. Multiple experienced staff left the project, including the WP lead. Resources were diverted for long periods of time due to high priority work such as HPAI outbreaks. Lockdowns and movement restrictions due to COVID-19 prevented face-to-face meetings to facilitate discussion and sharing of results and also led to delays in other WP deliverables giving less time to incorporate results.

In WP6, the workshops were initially planned to be held in conjunction with conferences relevant to the project. This plan was discarded because of the COVID-19 pandemic and replaced with online workshops. Despite the deviation from the original plan, the workshops which did take place were considered successful with many attendees from many countries in Europe as well as participants from other parts of the world including Africa ensuring wide dissemination.

Overall, some modifications had to be made, mainly due to the pandemic but the objectives could still be addressed as planned. In BIOPIGEE, outdoor farming systems were considered. Although the sample of outdoor farms may be representative of current European production within the dataset, a larger sample size of outdoor farms would be needed to be included in the future to validate the measures for these farms. Besides, more knowledge on HEV and its control measures is needed. Comparison with ASF findings is desirable also with regard to supplementation of pathogen related check lists in both ways. Finally, cost/economy information on measures is still scarce and important to increase for reliable calculations.

5. Progress of the project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
21	D-JRP21-WP1.2	First draft of data management plan finished	M30	M34 (website)	The DMP was uploaded to the project website and public in the CDP tool. It gets repeatedly updated in a shared document and changes transferred to CDP; OHEJP DMP group recommends to upload only the final DMP to Zenodo.	8
21	D-JRP21-WP1.4	Project report 1st year submitted	M36	M36	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/4361090	8 (reporting)
21	D-JRP21-WP1.13	Project report 2nd year submitted	M49	M49	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/5930342	8
21	D-JRP21-WP1.19	Revised data management plan submitted	M60	M60	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/7429754	8
21	D-JRP21-WP1.23	Final project report submitted	M60	M60	Going to be public under link https://zenodo.org/record/7429770	
21	D-JRP21-WP2.1	Biosecurity protocol (addressing measures to control Salmonella and HEV) designed for data collection in the field	M28	M29 (44 zenodo)	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/5336900	2

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
21	D-JRP21-WP2.8	Quantified biosecurity effectiveness from applied biosecurity protocol at slaughterhouses	M42	M48	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/5774876	4
21	D-JRP21-WP2.9	Quantified biosecurity effectiveness from applied biosecurity protocol at farm	M42	M48	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/5792859	4
21	D-JRP21-WP2.12	Produce report on evidence gathered by field studies	M54	M54	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/6780124	8
21	D-JRP21-WP2.18	Report on correlation of biosecurity practice with HEV sequences to WP5 and 6, sequence analysis of hepatitis E to HEVnet	M57	M58	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/7267862	5
21	D-JRP21-WP3.5	Method for testing persistence of infectious HEV in surface microlayers	M36	M42	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/4940091 ; was delayed due to COVID-19 pandemic and consequences	2
21	D-JRP21-WP3.6	HEV infectivity assay available	M36	M36	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/5242819	2
21	D-JRP21-WP3.7	Assessed methods for testing disinfectants on Salmonella in biofilm	M40	M44	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/5211242	2

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
21	D-JRP21-WP3.14	Information on the persistence of infectious HEV in surface microlayers/biofilm	48	M58	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/7231931	
21	D-JRP21-WP3.19	Information on the effect of different disinfectants on Salmonella in biofilm	M56	M56	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/7023490	2
21	D-JRP21-WP3.20	HEV infectivity test adapted for testing of HEVs in biofilm	M48	M48	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/5793040	1
21	D-JRP21-WP4.11	Model Output: Number of animal cases with and without biosecurity measures	M56	M56	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/6974303	7
21	D-JRP21-WP4.16	Economic calculation	M57	M57	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/7085855	7
21	D-JRP21-WP4.17	Model output: Number of human cases with and without biosecurity measures	M57	M58	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/7180805	7
21	D-JRP21-WP5.21	Benchmark system for effectiveness of biosecurity practice finished and forwarded to WP1 and WP6	M58	M58	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/7268326	4

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
21	D-JRP21-WP6.3	Workshop 1 completed		M56	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/6974588 National events were visited for dissemination and exchange of thoughts with stakeholders (instead of organising one international onsite workshop at the beginning of the project which was cancelled due to the pandemic situation).	8
21	D-JRP21-WP6.4	BIOPIGEE Flyer	M32	M32	Brief information when contacting potential new collaborators, experts for our panel, recruiting farmers, and as general dissemination to public) https://zenodo.org/record/4009015	8
21	D-JRP21-WP6.10	Workshop 2 completed	M48	M48	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/5806257	
21	D-JRP21-WP6.15	Biosecurity protocol on slaughterhouse provided	M48	M48	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/5772529	2
21	D-JRP21-WP6.22	Provision of information on best biosecurity practice to farming schools	M58	M60	Going to be public under Zenodo link https://zenodo.org/record/7429810	6
21	D-JRP21-WP6.24	Project web-content developed	M60	M60	Going to be public under Zenodo link https://zenodo.org/record/7429783	8
21	D-JRP21-WP6.25	A support tool (Excel) for calculation of cost effectiveness of preventive biosecurity measures developed	M60	M60	Going to be public under Zenodo link https://zenodo.org/record/7429826	8

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, other comments</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
21	D-JRP21-WP6.26	Workshop 3 completed	M58	M58	Two online workshops held for dissemination of results on effective biosecurity measures in 1) primary production and 2) at slaughter in September 2022, public, https://zenodo.org/record/7259005	8
21	D-JRP21-WP6.27	Provision of biosecurity protocol and of benchmark of biosecurity practice	M60	M59	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/7351107	8
21	D-JRP21-WP6.28	Workshop 4 completed	n.a. (additional workshop)	M58	Public, https://zenodo.org/record/7181040	8

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
21	M-JRP21-01	Kick-off meeting successfully organised	M26	Yes	
21	M-JRP21-02	Questionnaire on biosecurity costs	M26	Yes, M27	Farm performance questions included. Biosecurity cost question excluded; data will be gathered from other sources.
21	M-JRP21-03	Relevant conferences for workshops to be held are identified	26	Yes (46)	Was delayed due to pandemic situation. It is planned to disseminate more findings in pre-conference-Workshop at the ESPHM on 11th March 2022
21	M-JRP21-04	Biosecurity protocol designed for Salmonella and HEV	M28	Yes	
21	M-JRP21-05	Relevant stakeholders identified	28	Yes (36)	Was postponed due to the current COVID-19 situation (no workshops took place yet); Instead of stakeholders, a list of experts for a panel in WP5-T4 has been expanded (online table, link in BIOPIGEE private webgroup). These experts were finally invited for an online workshop to be hold in December 2021.
21	M-JRP21-06	Appropriate websites or other online channels for dissemination identified	30	Yes	List of web sites is being filled in an online table (link in BIOPIGEE private webgroup); Content will be continuously updated throughout the project
21	M-JRP21-07	Workshop 1 completed	30	Yes (47)	WP-leader decision: The workshop was cancelled due to COVID-19-outbreak, instead national information events in 2021/22 are

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
					planned (in Germany, animal health services were informed about our findings and discussed with at their conference in Nov 2021)
21	M-JRP21-08	Design of field study protocols	M32	Yes	
21	M-JRP21-09	First part of meta-analysis finished	36	Yes (38)	A literature review and meta-analysis was carried out. Was delayed due to partners involved in covid-testing and missing personnel for 4 months at BfR
21	M-JRP21-10	Salmonella strains for testing are collected	M36	Yes	
21	M-JRP21-11	HEV infectivity assay available	M36	Yes	
21	M-JRP21-12	Mid-term meeting successfully organized	39	Yes	
21	M-JRP21-13	Application of protocols across countries	40	Yes (46)	Was delayed and sample size slightly reduced in a few countries due to pandemic situation and restrictions for visiting farms.
21	M-JRP21-14	Relevant stakeholders re-identified	36	Yes (41)	As stated for M-JRP21-05, an expert panel is addressed instead. This was re-identified in M41.
21	M-JRP21-15	Transmission model adaptation based on available data	45	yes	Completed. The baseline QMRA models for Salmonella and HEV have been completed utilizing relevant recent data.
21	M-JRP21-16	Test methods to be used in JRP21-WP3-T2-ST2 are selected	40	No (46)	Milestone completed. Each lab will use the already locally established biofilm testing method for WP3-T2-ST2.

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
21	M-JRP21-17	Produce summary of evidence of slaughterhouse biosecurity effectiveness	42	Yes (48)	Development of questionnaire took longer than planned (review of peer-reviewed papers; consideration of technique in all countries; common understanding of relevant biosecurity measures and formulation of questions; translations; implementation into survey tool; test runs; data protection issues). The questionnaire was prepared and the survey was carried out in summer 2021.
21	M-JRP21-18	Workshop 2 completed	40	Yes (48)	Was postponed to the second half of 2021, due to pandemic situation, changed to a virtual workshop with the expert panel from WP5-T4.
21	M-JRP21-19	Completion of farm visits and lab work	54	56	completed (NL continues with visits which can complement BIOPIGEE results)
21	M-JRP21-20	Application of appropriate economic methods based on available data	51	yes	Completed. Economic methods were selected for application. Working document is created, to be updated if methods have to be adjusted.
21	M-JRP21-21	Uploading of sequences to HEVnet	54	56	Completed
21	M-JRP21-22	Matching of different simulation model approaches to one	55	yes	Completed. The different models developed in WP4 have been developed to ensure that the relevant outputs of one model can act as inputs to another.
21	M-JRP21-23	Relevant disinfectants are tested against Salmonella in biofilm	56	yes	Completed

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
21	M-JRP21-24	Relevant disinfectants are tested against HEV in surface microlayers/biofilms	56	yes	A pilot study on HEV stability in relation to disinfectants has been executed
21	M-JRP21-25	Finalized data integration from WP2-4 into catalogue of biosecurity measures	59		ongoing, depends on delayed tasks; existing content has been used for other tasks
21	M-JRP21-26	Finalized literature review/meta-analysis	50	53	finalised (was delayed because of change in staff), results are currently being written up in a manuscript by the task group
21	M-JRP21-27	Economic model for the assessments of profitability of biosecurity measures	57	57	finalised, parameters for economic assessment identified and model to calculate the profitability set up. Cost-benefit analysis was carried out with the available results from the QMRA.
21	M-JRP21-28	Predicted effectiveness of specific biosecurity measures from machine learning approach incorporated in catalogue	57	n.a.	cancelled, appeared not anymore useful and necessary for informing the biosecurity catalogue because other tasks (literature review, field studies) fed already the catalogue. Instead, ASReview was used in WP5-T2 to partly automate and complement the comprehensive literature search. Thereby, the following WP5-T5 benchmark task was well informed.
21	M-JRP21-29	Expert panel ranked biosecurity practice	51	yes	finalised, manuscript has been submitted
21	M-JRP21-30	Information on best biosecurity practice to farming schools ready to be provided	M58	Yes (M60)	nearly finalized, additional content was added to inform also about other project outcomes and aspects

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Date of achievement	Comments
21	M-JRP21-31	Relevant stakeholders re-identified	M58	2022-07-05	Relevant stakeholders re-assessed for the invitation to the final workshops.
21	M-JRP21-32	Benchmark system for effectiveness/relevance of biosecurity practice finished	M58	Yes (M58)	completed
21	M-JRP21-33	Final meeting successfully organized	M58	Yes (M58)	completed
21	M-JRP21-34	The Excel support tool for cost effectiveness calculations distributed	M60	Yes (M60+)	As of end of M60 the tool is being tested for comprehensibility and user friendliness. Distribution will only start 2023.
21	M-JRP21-35	Workshop 3 and 4 completed	M58	Yes (M57)	completed
21	M-JRP21-36	Project web-content disseminated online	M60	Yes (M60)	Finalised, all outputs, respective DOIs and links are listed in the information material for complete access to project results. Distribution will start end of 2022.

6. Follow-up of the recommendations and comments by the Ethics Advisors

The Ethics Advisors have evaluated your project and have approved your replies.

However, if you have any comments related to ethics due to modifications of the work plan, new guidelines in any of the partner institutes of the consortium, or other, please write them here:

No comments.

7. Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Manuscript status	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Propagation du virus de l'hépatite E de la case à la filière: analyse de réseaux complexes et modélisation, JRP conference/paper DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6091598 https://zenodo.org/record/6091598	published	Yes	Yes	No
Complex network analysis to understand trading partnership in French swine production, PlosOne DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0266457 https://zenodo.org/record/6458445#.YnkdKehBxwQ	published	Yes	No	Yes (about 1400 €)
What is a biosecurity measure? A definition proposal for animal production and linked processing operations DOI: 10.1016/j.onehlt.2022.100433 https://zenodo.org/record/7143533	published	Yes	No	Yes (about 2000 € without taxes)

Prioritization of pig farm biosecurity for control of Salmonella and hepatitis E virus infections; results of a European Expert Opinion Elicitation	submitted	Yes	TBC	TBC
Effectiveness of pig farm biosecurity measures for the control of Salmonella on European farms – a case control study	submitted	Yes	TBC	TBC
Detection of HEV RNA by one-step real-time RT-PCR in far-row-to-finish pig farms in Bulgaria	submitted	Yes	TBC	TBC
Slaughterhouse biosecurity measures for Salmonella control with quantified effectiveness: a review	under preparation	Yes	TBC	TBC
Review of the implementation of effective biosecurity practices, related to Salmonella and hepatitis E virus control, in a selection of European pig slaughterhouses	under preparation	Yes	TBC	TBC
A quantitative microbiological risk assessment for transmission of HEV in the pork production chain.	under preparation	Yes	TBC	TBC
Surveillance of Hepatitis E virus circulation in Italian pig farms	under preparation	Yes	TBC	TBC
Sequence diversity of Hepatitis E virus from European pig farms	under preparation	Yes	TBC	TBC
Protective Biosecurity Measures to reduce hepatitis E virus in European pig farms	under preparation	Yes	TBC	TBC
Biosecurity measures reducing Salmonella spp., hepatitis E virus and pathogenic Escherichia coli prevalence in pig farms: A systematic review and meta-analysis.	under preparation	Yes	TBC	TBC

Additional output

Posters

- Jones, H., Smith, R.P., Burow, E., on behalf of the BIOPIGEE consortium (2022). Effective biosecurity measures for the control of *Salmonella* in European pig farms. Poster at the OHEJP ASM 11-13.04.2022. Orvieto/online.
- Ianiro G., Pavoni E., Alborali G., Guadagno F., Delibato E., Treglia I., De Sabato L., Monini M., Ostanello F., Di Bartolo I. (2022). Molecular tracing of dissemination routes of *Salmonella* spp, Hepatitis E virus and other viruses as fecal indicators in pigs at slaughterhouse. Poster at the OHEJP ASM 11-13.04.2022. Orvieto/online. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6646338>
- Ianiro G., Pavoni E., Aprea G., Romantini R., Alborali G., D'Angelantonio D., Garofolo G., Scattolini S., De Sabato L., Ostanello F., Di Bartolo I. (2022). Presence of *Salmonella* spp. And Hepatitis E virus in Italian pig farms. Poster at the OHEJP ASM 11-13.04.2022. Orvieto/online. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6638970>
- Meester M., Tobias T., Meulenbroek C., Hakze-van der Honing R., van Oort S., Bouwknecht M., Stegeman A., van der Poel W.H.M. (2022). Prevalence of HEV in finishing pigs: cross-sectional exploration of farm specific patterns and evaluation of sampling. Poster at the OHEJP ASM 11-13.04.2022. Orvieto/online. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6566927>
- Kozyra, I., Zając, M., Żmudzki, J., Dors, A., Skrzypiec, E., Wasyl, D., Rzeżutka, A. (2022). Epidemiological significance of *Salmonella* and hepatitis E virus (HEV) occurrence in fattening pigs in Poland. Poster at the OHEJP ASM 11-13.04.2022. Orvieto/online. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6673709>
- Hammami, P., Widgren, S., Grosbois, V., Apolloni, A., Rose, N., Andraud, M. (2021). Multi-levels Hepatitis E Virus Spread In Various Epidemiological Contexts: Combining Complex Network Analysis & Disease Transmission Model. Poster at the 8th International Conference on Infectious Disease Dynamics (Epidemics 8), online. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5786494>
- Huber, N., Zoche-Golob, V., Sassu, E. L., Prigge, C., Käsbohrer, A., Andraud, M., D'Angelantonio, D., Viltrop, A., Niine, T., Hammami, P., Zmudzki, J., Jones, H., Burow, E. (2022). What is a biosecurity measure? A definition proposal for farms and linked processing operations. Poster at the ONE2022 21.-24.06.2022., Brussel/online.
- Smith, R., Jones, H., Burow, E. (2022). *Salmonella* presence on European pig farms. I3S International Symposium *Salmonella* & Salmonellosis 20.-22.06.222. Saint-Malo. <https://zenodo.org/record/7054296>
- Dors, A., Wasyl, D., Rzeżutka, A., Karbowski, P., Szalkowski, W., Zmudzki, J. (2022). A survey on external biosecurity in selected commercial Polish pig farms. Poster at the ONE2022 21.-24.06.2022., Brussel/online.
- Burow, E., Zoche-Golob, V., Tobias, T., Sassu, E. L., Galpó, E., Prigge, C., Smith, R. P., Sjölund, M. (2022). Expert opinion on biosecurity measures for controlling *Salmonella* and hepatitis E virus in pig farming - findings of the OHEJP BIOPIGEE project. Poster at the ONE2022 21.-24.06.2022., Brussel/online.
- Niine, T., Viltrop, A., Nurmoja, I., Smith, R., Burow, E. (2022). The best biosecurity practices in European abattoirs in regards to *Salmonella* and hepatitis E virus. Poster at the ONE2022 21.-24.06.2022., Brussel/online. <https://zenodo.org/record/7032155>
- Jones, H., Smith, R. P., Burow, E. (2022). Effective biosecurity measures for the control of

Salmenlla in European pig farms. Poster at 16th International Symposium of Veterinary Epidemiology and Economics (ISVEE), 07.-12.08.2022, Halifax, CA.

- Meester, M., Tobias, T., van der Poel, W. (2022). Biosecurity practices to reduce risk of hepatitis E virus in European pig farms. Poster at 16th International Symposium of Veterinary Epidemiology and Economics (ISVEE), 07.-12.08.2022, Halifax, CA.
- Meester, M., Tobias, T., van der Poel, W. (2022). Sensitivity and specificity of pen-level sampling methods for hepatitis E virus detection in fattening pigs. Poster at 16th International Symposium of Veterinary Epidemiology and Economics (ISVEE), 07.-12.08.2022, Halifax, CA.
- Osland, A.M, Oastler, C. Brook, E. Gosling, B. Arvand, M. Richter, A.M, Konrat, K. Asal, B. Vestby. L.K. (2022). Effect of Glutaraldehyde on biofilm-associated wild type *Salmonella*. Poster will be presented at Eurobiofilms 2022. 31.8.22-3.9.22, Mallorca, Spain
- Hammami, P., Widgren, S., Grosbois, V., Apolloni, A., Rose, N., Andraud, M. (2022). Multi-levels hepatitis E virus spread in various epidemiological contexts: combining complex network analysis & disease transmission model. Poster at the Epidemics conference. <https://zenodo.org/record/5786494>
- Hammami, P (2021). Live animal movement - Understnad trade partners choices to predict cahins of contact. SVEPM 2021.
- McCarthy, C. (2021). BIOPIGEE: Modelling of the cost and effectiveness of biosecurity measures. OHEJP ASM 2021.
- Bester, C. (2022). Development of an economic model to assess the cost-effectiveness of biosecurity measures to reduce the burden of Salmonella and Hepatitis E virus in the pork production chain. ISAH 2022.

Oral presentations

- Niine, T., Viltrop, A., Nurmoja, I., Smith, R., Burow, E. (2022). Biosecurity measures in European slaughterhouses to prevent the contamination of pig carcasses with *Salmonella*. Konverentsi "terve loom ja tervislik toit 2022" artiklikogumik (Estonian conference), 157–160. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6355316>
- Viltrop, A. (2022). Biosecurity of *Salmonella* from Estonian pig farms perspective. Estonian Officials Veterinarian Training day.
- Burow, E. (presentation), Zoche-Golob, V. (abstract), Aprea, G., Sjölund, M., for the BIOPIGEE consortium (2022). Biosecurity measures reducing Hepatitis E Virus in pig herds – findings of the OHEJP project BIOPIGEE. Oral presentation at German conference 22. Fachtagung für Fleisch- und Geflügelfleischhygiene, 1.-2. March 2022, Berlin, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6524126>
- Hammami, P., Widgren, S., Grosbois, V., Apolloni, A., Rose, N., Andraud, M. (2022). Spread of hepatitis E virus from pens to the national industry: complex network analysis and modelling. 54th Journées de la Recherche Porcine (JRP), 2nd February 2022, online. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6091598>
- Hammami, P., Widgren, S., Grosbois, V., Apolloni, A., Rose, N., Andraud, M. (2022). Propagation du virus de l'hépatite E de la case à la filière : analyse de réseaux complexes et modélisation. Talk at the Junior Researcher Programme conference <https://zenodo.org/record/6091598>

- Burow, E., N. Huber, E. Galipó, R. Smith (2022). Effective and prioritised biosecurity practice to control *Salmonella* in pig farming - findings from the BIOPIGEE project. Oral presentation at HealthyLivestock conference, 16.06.2022, hybrid
- Burow, E., Schulze-Horsel, T., Harlizius, J., Rostalski, A., Smith, R., Zoche-Golob, V., Galipó, E., Waller, E., Jones, H., Sjölund, M., Käsbohrer, A. (2022). Biosicherheitsmaßnahmen zur Kontrolle von Salmonellen und Hepatitis E Viren in der europäischen Schweinehaltung - OHEJP Projekt BIOPIGEE. Biosecurity measures for controlling *Salmonella* and hepatitis E virus in European pig farming - OHEJP project BIOPIGEE. DACH Epidemiologietagung 2022, 31.08.-02.09.2022, Oldenburg.
- Galipó, E., Zoche-Golob, V., Sassu E. L., Prigge, C., Sjölund, M., Tobias, T., Rzesutka, A., Smith, R., Burow, E. (2022). Pig farm biosecurity for control of *Salmonella* and hepatitis E virus infections – a survey of European experts. Oral presentation at the OHEJP ASM 11-13.04.2022. Orvieto/online.
- Hammami, P. (2021). Complex network analysis and Exponential Random Graph Models: Epidemiological implications of network structures. Modah 2021.
- Hammami, P. (2021). Multi-level Hepatitis E Virus Spread in various epidemiological contexts: combining complex network analysis & disease transmission models. CCS 2021.
- Wilkins, N. (2022). A farm-to-consumption quantitative microbiological risk assessment for hepatitis E in pigs. Presented at 16th International Symposium of Veterinary Epidemiology and Economics (ISVEE), 07.-12.08.2022, Halifax, CA.

Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.

In WP6, additional outcomes like support tool for e.g. farmers, information/education material for farming pupils, website information and two more workshops (in September 2022) for the exchange of ideas with stakeholders were planned. The workshops took place with broad international audience. The education material and website presentations is in work.

Are there any outcomes of this project that are already discussed or even implemented and in use at any institute of the project consortium, at stakeholders' organisations (ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), or at the level of national authorities?

Outcomes of the project have been discussed at the following institutes of the project consortium:

At work group level at APHA, SVA and BfR.

At department level at APHA and BfR

At institute level at BfR.

A representative of EFSA was present at the final project meeting of BIOPIGEE in order to discuss the outcomes.

Furthermore results of the project are going to be presented and discussed at the UK Pig Health and Welfare Council (PHWC).

8. One Health impact

The OHEJP BIOPIGEE project aimed at identifying effective and cost-efficient biosecurity measures to control hepatitis E virus (HEV) and *Salmonella* occurrence in European pig farming. These two pathogens represent important zoonotic organisms.

Correspondingly the comprehensive literature reviews, field and experimental studies, expert opinion surveys and risk modelling which had been done provide a valuable knowledge base for international stakeholders involved in the domain of zoonoses. The outcomes include guidance for farmers, veterinarians, consultants and slaughterhouses in European countries in form of illustrative flyers and web content to inform stakeholders, incl. collaborating farm education centres. The material should provide reliable and cost-efficient guidance on the reduction of *Salmonella* and HEV spread in animals and humans (through occupational exposure) which add important information for monitoring and regulation in order to advance One Health.

Regional and national authorities could pick up the material produced, translate them into their regional language(s) and use them. It is also possible to develop the material further or adapt it to the local needs.

During the process we reached out to academics and practitioners in the field particularly in the three workshops organized by BIOPIGEE. But we also presented and discussed our results various national events. Namely at a 2-days-hybrid event of the North Rhine-Westphalian Pig Health Service which took place at the Chamber of Agriculture in Bad Sassendorf, Germany where we engaged with the participants of veterinarians, representatives of agriculture and the pig industry as well as laboratory staff and researchers. During the event, a contact was made with an advisory service on biosecurity practices in pig production in Baden-Wuerttemberg, and in a subsequent telephone meeting information was exchanged in more detail on measure effectiveness and the interest and use of farmers to implement knowledge. Another network was established with the agricultural education centre of the North Rhine-Westphalian Chamber of Agriculture and a web meeting was arranged after the conference to discuss how best to disseminate project results to agricultural students. Further exchange was agreed.

Then we went to the annual conference of the Institute of the Veterinary Medicine and Animal Sciences of the Estonian University of Life Sciences which was attended by farmers, food industry representatives, and state officials of the field. There results of the BIOPIGEE research were presented and discussed in two presentations in two sections of the event.

Also in Estonia we presented our work in a seminar which took place for the animal health officials from the headquarter and regional offices of the Agriculture and Food Board. The seminar was organized by the Estonian Veterinary and Food Laboratory (VFL).

The information about biosecurity with respect to *Salmonella* might help to inform scientist and risk managers who study AMR in pig production to mitigate resistant versions of *Salmonella* along the pig production chain.

9. Data Management Plan

The project DMP should be finalized on the CDP tool, all the data should be made public and the DMP should be extracted from the CDP Tool and uploaded to Zenodo.

Zenodo link to be provided here.

<https://zenodo.org/record/7429754>

10. Future dissemination activities

Main stakeholders are farmers and vets. The main materials produced during the project are support tools like checklists, guidance documents and a cost-benefit model. The PMT and Communication Team can help in providing easy to access storage of above mentioned materials and help dissemination by featuring these materials at events with agricultural stakeholders as well or in publications in farmers magazines.

11. List of dissemination and communication activities

Name of the activity:	BIOPIGEE Online Workshop: Biosecurity measures to control Salmonella and hepatitis E virus (HEV) along the pig production chain in Europe		
Date:	14 December 2021		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories. Include hyperlink, if relevant. Zenodo grants the open access, it could be used as a repository for the presentations, posters, and other dissemination materials.			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	No
Organisation of a Workshop	Yes	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	62	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	BIOPIGEE Online Workshop: Biosecurity Measures to Control Salmonella and Hepatitis E Virus (HEV) in European Primary Pig Production		
Date:	14 September 2022		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories. Include hyperlink, if relevant. Zenodo grants the open access, it could be used as a repository for the presentations, posters, and other dissemination materials.			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	No
Organisation of a Workshop	Yes	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	27	Media	
Industry	54	Investors	
Civil Society	30	Customers	
General Public		Other	40
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	BIOPIGEE Online Workshop: Biosecurity Measures in Slaughterhouses to Control Salmonella and Hepatitis E Virus (HEV)		
Date:	16 September 2022		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories. Include hyperlink, if relevant. Zenodo grants the open access, it could be used as a repository for the presentations, posters, and other dissemination materials.			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	No
Organisation of a Workshop	Yes	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)		Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers		For this event we could not identify the categories of the participants	Over 100 participants

Name of the activity:	2-days-hybrid event of the North Rhine-Westphalian Pig Health Service		
Date:	25 and 26 November 2021		
Place:	Chamber of Agriculture in Bad Sassendorf, Germany		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories. Include hyperlink, if relevant. Zenodo grants the open access, it could be used as a repository for the presentations, posters, and other dissemination materials.			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	No
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	Yes
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)		Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers		We do not know how the more than 100 attendees were distributed in terms of their backgrounds	>100

Name of the activity:	Annual conference of the Institute of the Veterinary Medicine and Animal Sciences of the Estonian University of Life Sciences 'Healthy Animal – Healthy Food'		
Date:	2 and 3 March 2022		
Place:	Estonian University of Life Sciences		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories. Include hyperlink, if relevant. Zenodo grants the open access, it could be used as a repository for the presentations, posters, and other dissemination materials.			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)		Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers		We do not know how the more than 200 attendees were distributed in terms of their backgrounds	>200

Name of the activity:	Seminar for the animal health officials from the headquarter and regional offices of the Agriculture and Food Board in Estonia		
Date:	12 May 2022		
Place:	Estonian Veterinary and Food Laboratory (VFL)		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories. Include hyperlink, if relevant. Zenodo grants the open access, it could be used as a repository for the presentations, posters, and other dissemination materials.			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	No
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	Yes
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)		Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society	27	Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

APPENDIX 1

This information is from the original Full Proposal of the project, submitted in 2018. It will help the evaluators when assessing the final report.

Please do not modify this part.

Objectives description

We will provide **advice to** farmers, veterinarians, authorities and the wider pig industry on the best practice with regards to biosecurity measures, with the help of a series of workshops, website-content, reports, support for farming schools, and a decision support tool (WP6). The guidance will concentrate on the effectiveness of biosecurity measures against Salmonella and HEV, but will also provide relevant information and discussion on their appropriateness for other pathogens of public health and pig health importance. BIOPIGEE will concentrate on farm-specific measures but will also include factors related to slaughterhouse and pig transport.

Biosecurity protocols with the focus on Salmonella and HEV occurrence in pig production and at abattoir will be developed and applied in partner countries. The included biosecurity measures will be evaluated with the help of surveillance data and sampling. Thanks to the strong collection of consortium members, **further studies** will be arranged to **investigate** effectiveness of biosecurity measures.

The biological **effectiveness and cost-effectiveness** of biosecurity measures will be determined through case-control and specific field studies involving the partner countries (WP2) and by the interpretation of outputs of a Quantitative microbial risk assessment, as well as economic effectiveness models (WP4).

Knowledge of effectiveness and costs of biosecurity measures will be collected from all WPs, alongside with research findings gathered from other studies and supplemented with information from machine learning, in a catalogue of biosecurity measures. Based on effective measures and the assessment of an expert panel, a benchmark of biosecurity practice relevant for reduction of Salmonella and HEV in pig production will be developed.

In the workshop series we will apply a **farm-to-fork** approach, connecting stakeholders along the food chain; from farmers to consumers (WP6).

The project will build on ongoing **EU-wide activities** by incorporating a selection of strong partners involved in the latest relevant activities and with mutual agreement to cooperate with HEV-net and the developer of BIOCHECK, Jeroen Dewulf.

Project abstract

Salmonella and HEV are zoonotic pathogens which are in general subclinical in pigs. Salmonellosis can cause gastrointestinal diseases in humans with over 90 thousand confirmed cases and 156 deaths in the EU in 2017. HEV infections in humans can be fatal; it is considered an emerging problem in the EU.

Biosecurity protocols are highly important tools to reduce the load of such pathogens along the food chain, leading to safe and healthy animal-derived food.

We built a dense network of European research organisations including public health from all European regions, joining expertise in veterinary epidemiology, microbiology, veterinary and human medicine, agronomy, econometrics, bacteriology. The proposed project concentrates on the pathogens Salmonella and HEV.

First in WP2, a biosecurity protocol for the primary production will be developed. Applying this protocol, herds in the project partners' countries identified as being at high or low pathogen risk will be assessed for their biosecurity to find best practice at different production stages. Additionally, field

and intervention studies will be completed in areas where current evidence is weak, e.g. effectiveness of management controls on HEV prevalence. Furthermore, a protocol for slaughterhouse biosecurity will be developed and applied in partner countries. The persistence of Salmonella, HEV and other pathogens in reservoirs (biofilms) will be evaluated in depth together with studies of disinfection effectiveness (WP3).

The consortium partners' disease transmission models (stochastic, network trade, quantitative microbial risk assessment) will be improved by newly gained empirical data.. Scenarios on country-specific biosecurity measures and on the measures' impact on human infection rate will be run. Results will be used to assess the economic profitability of the implementation of standard and specific intervention measures along the pig supply chain and to assess projected future pork-product derived human salmonellosis cases (WP4).

A catalogue of biosecurity measures will be continuously filled with the findings on the measures' effectiveness and costs for Salmonella and HEV in WP2-5. A benchmarking of biosecurity practice (measures, categories and overall) will be developed which considers different production stages as well as European regions. Finally, dissemination activities (WP6) include comprehensive education material for e.g. farming schools and online-use, a support tool to calculate cost effective measures and a workshop series that will connect researchers and stakeholders and help to exchange knowledge and experience all along the chain "from farm to fork", with special focus on primary production.

Background

Human cases of salmonellosis decreased from 2008 to 2013 but have stagnated on still high levels in the recent years in the EU (EFSA & ECDC 2017). About 10-20% of Salmonella infections in EU may be attributable to the pig reservoir (EFSA 2010) but lead seldomly to clinical symptoms in pigs. For protection of human health, it's the common aim to reduce Salmonella prevalence in pork (i.e. avoidance of contamination during slaughter/ decontamination of carcasses) and, along the whole pig production chain (i.e. avoid infection and transmission) since Salmonella are present at each production stage from birth to carcass of pigs (Bolton et al. 2013).

Two European baseline studies investigated prevalence in 24 European countries between 2006 and 2008 (Regulation EC 2160/2003). In tendency, breeding sows as well as fattening pigs were found to show higher Salmonella prevalence in southern and western countries compared to northern and eastern countries. However, only few, mainly production related, aspects were investigated as potential risk factors. One of the few promising key factors appeared by seasonal effect in the third quarter of the year.

However, it remained unclear which biosecurity factors would be relevant.

Consequently, many countries have implemented surveillance/ control strategies on farm in the recent 20 years. Today, there is still a high proportion of Salmonella positive carcasses (EFSA & ECDC 2017) and many herds still have high Salmonella prevalence which indicates that guidance to address this problem is required (Arguello et al. 2018).

In the baseline study, the risk factors, herd/group size, production stage, flooring type, feed origin and type of feed were identified as being relevant for sows and rearing pigs. However, cleaning & disinfection and rodent/birds/fly control were not included even though potentially relevant for Salmonella prevalence in sows.

Several more recent studies investigated single or a mixture of biosecurity (e.g. kind of disinfection, personnel hygiene) to reduce occurrence of Salmonella in pig farming (e.g. Gosling et al. 2017, Gotter et al. 2012). Results were partly contradicting or unclear so that a promising protocol of biosecurity measures was not obvious, nor clearly proven to be effective for European production systems.

Moreover, some measures (interventions at breeding, abattoir) were described to be most effective in high prevalent conditions while others (feed and biosecurity measures) to be more effective in low prevalent condition (Hill et al. 2016). Hence, protocols for specific conditions (production stage and prevalence status) are needed.

Even though prevalence of Salmonella decreases with increased biosecurity in an intervention study, the willingness to adopt biosecurity measures is in conflict with the inverse economic cost (Fraser et al. 2010, UK) and costs of intervention overweighting the savings even if the measures were effective (Gavin et al. 2018). However, as a base for taking decisions, evidence based knowledge is needed with regard to different production stages, countries and pathogens.

Hepatitis E virus (HEV) is a small RNA quasi-enveloped virus causing hepatitis in humans. The infection can be asymptomatic or causing an acute self-limiting (mortality 1%) disease. Chronic infections have been observed in immunocompromised individuals. Over the last 10 years in Europe, the number of cases has significantly increased with most infections being locally acquired (Aspinall et al., 2017). Genotypes 3 and 4 are zoonotic, infecting swine, wild boar, and occasionally other animal species (rabbit, deer). HEV- 3 and HEV-4 cause autochthonous cases in Europe. Although the source of infection is mostly unknown, the foodborne route is considered major for HEV-3 and -4 transmissions to humans in Europe. Pigs and wild boars are the main reservoirs of HEV. Sporadic cases and small outbreaks in humans linked to consumption of raw or undercooked meat or liver from pigs and wild boar were reported in Europe. The HEV-3 is the most frequent genotype in both pigs and wild boar in Europe.

No baseline studies exist for HEV. However, it is clear that in pigs the HEV-3 is widespread and predominant in Europe. The individual seroprevalence increases with age up to 90% in adult pigs (6 months of age), while at farm level prevalences ranges from 30 to 98%. Detection of viral RNA in animals at farms has been also frequently described varying a lot between European countries (1-89%) but also between farms in the same country (from 12.8 to 72.5% in Italy) (Salines et al., 2017).

Comparing results is difficult since samples tested (feces, bile, liver) and methods used differ between stocks. However, all studies converged in the occurrence of HEV infection in pigs after loss of maternal immunity with a decrease occurrence of infection in animals >15 weeks of age. The observed difference may also reflect different animal exposure to the virus (early or late animal mixing or farm management) and different specific risk factors of the farm under investigation. The risk factors have been rarely measured. A higher risk of infections was observed in farms with >1000 sows, higher seroprevalence was observed in organic farms than in conventional farms. No differences were observed in farrow-to-finish or farrow to weaning farm (Salines et al., 2017). Here, the virus is transmitted by fecal-oral route and a high quantity of the virus was seen in feces contributing to environmental contamination. Naive animals introduced in the contaminated pens or farms may be infected as well, determining a persistence of the virus in farms.

In general, farm internal biosecurity measures may have a role in limiting occurrence and persistence of the virus in farms, but how and which measures may influence this is largely unknown.

Therefore, BIOPIGEE aims to review and to generate additional knowledge on effective as well as costeffective biosecurity measures for Salmonella and HEV that can be advised to further focus on in herds and countries in order to reduce prevalence.

Arguello et al., 2018. Surveillance Data Highlights Feed Form, Biosecurity, and Disease Control as significant Factors Associated with Salmonella Infection on Farrow-to-Finish Pig Farms. Frontiers in microbiology 9, 187; Aspinall et al., 2017. Hepatitis E virus infection in Europe: surveillance and descriptive epidemiology of confirmed cases, 2005 to 2015. Euro surveillance: bulletin Europeen sur les maladies transmissibles = European communicable disease bulletin, 22; Bolton et al., 2013. A study of Salmonella in pigs from birth to carcass: serotypes, genotypes, antibiotic resistance and virulence profiles. International journal of food microbiology 160, 298-303; EFSA, 2017. Scientific Opinion on a Quantitative Microbiological Risk Assessment of Salmonella in slaughter and breeder pigs. EFSA Journal

2010; 8(4):1547; doi: 10.2903/j.efsa.2010.1547; EFSA & ECDC, 2017. The European Union summary report on trends and sources of zoonoses, zoonotic agents and food-borne outbreaks in 2016.

EFSA Journal 2017;15(12):5077; doi: 10.2903/j.efsa.2017.5077; Fraser et al., 2010. Reducing *Campylobacter* and *Salmonella* infection: two studies of the economic cost and attitude to adoption of on-farm biosecurity measures. *Zoonoses and public health* 57, e109-115; Gavin, Simons, et al., 2018. A cost-benefit assessment of *Salmonella*-control strategies in pigs reared in the United Kingdom. *Preventive veterinary medicine* 160, 54-62; Gosling et al., 2017. Efficacy of disinfectants and detergents intended for a pig farm environment where *Salmonella* is present.

Veterinary microbiology 204, 46-53; Gotter et al., 2012. Main risk factors for *Salmonella*-infections in pigs in north-western Germany. *Preventive veterinary medicine* 106, 301-307; Hill et al., 2016. Assessing the Effectiveness of On-Farm and Abattoir Interventions in Reducing Pig Meat-

Borne *Salmonellosis* within E.U. Member States. Risk analysis: an official publication of the Society for Risk Analysis 36, 546-560; Salines et al., 2017. From the epidemiology of hepatitis E virus (HEV) within the swine reservoir to public health risk mitigation strategies: a comprehensive review. *Veterinary research*, 48, 31.

Progress beyond state of the art

Former relevant projects investigated biosecurity practice in order to gain knowledge on measures relevant for pig and human health e.g. the European projects EFFORT and MINAPIG on antimicrobial use and resistance in pig production and the German project EsRAM on biosecurity and ESBL in broiler production. However, the effectiveness of biosecurity measures for the reduction of *Salmonella* or HEV prevalence in the pig production chain has not yet been sufficiently assessed on a joint European level - which is crucial.

BIOPIGEE will establish a protocol of biosecurity measures relevant for reducing occurrence of *Salmonella* and HEV in the pig production chain, harmonized among countries. It will further link prevalence data with biosecurity information at farm level in at least ten countries. BIOPIGEE will produce a catalogue of biosecurity measures and their effectiveness and costs towards limitation/reduction of *Salmonella* and HEV occurrence. Biosecurity practices will be benchmarked. As different production stages will be considered and diverse countries will contribute, countries with high as well as low pathogen prevalence will find information on key points to improve their respective situation.

Furthermore, BIOPIGEE will advance in the calculation of cost-effectiveness of biosecurity measures, as in the proposed project, the effectiveness will be compared among countries.

Next, progress will be achieved in the disinfection domain, where distinct disinfectants are tested to eliminate pathogens in biofilm.

The project will further advance knowledge on slaughterhouse biosecurity practices, as a detailed study with seven partnering countries will evaluate carcass contamination/cross-contamination to define best practice.

Project aims

The project BIOPIGEE aims at:

Filling the One Health approach with life

In order to integrate complementary expertise from as many fields of One Health as possible we formed for this project a strong consortium consisting of 15 partners from 12 countries and including veterinarians, doctors, microbiologists, food & agricultural scientists, epidemiologists and

environmental scientists. They will not work separately but in collaboration to reduce the burden of *Salmonella* and HEV infections in Europe. National public entities have been connected to build a stable and sustainable European partnership. The project incorporates existing networks of partners of European organisations and includes partners involved with ongoing European research, reference laboratory activities and surveillance in the field of zoonotic pathogens from pig production.

Strive towards alignment

It is of great importance for us to advance European harmonisation in standards and methods. That is why we will build up a new protocol to assess biosecurity standards, which collates as much knowledge as we can bring together with the help of specialists from 12 countries. For this, we collect, compare and evaluate existing methodologies and protocols and distill all essential information into one protocol. For the benchmarking of biosecurity practice, relevant for *Salmonella* and HEV occurrence, an expert panel of different stakeholders will help to harmonize the assessment.

Build competences that outlast the project duration

We are convinced that the special consortium that we formed will build up a protocol and relationships among members that will outlast the time period of the proposed project. Personal contacts that will arise from our cooperation and the working towards a common goal will build those ties. Care has been taken to ensure that all partners will benefit from the project results: All partners (and beyond) are provided with a harmonised protocol, that will catalogue biosecurity measures at farm level and slaughterhouse and allow for the selection of measures that are effective within their specific country context. The developed benchmarking system will offer an assessment of biosecurity practice for reducing *Salmonella* and HEV occurrence at different production stages. Additionally, a tool to calculate the cost effectiveness of these measures, a workshop series for further training and training material on biosecurity in pig production farms will be provided.

Spread the word

It is our common goal to disseminate project findings. Consequently WP6 was designed to lead this special task. Within WP6, two biosecurity protocols (primary production/slaughterhouse) will be published, a catalogue and benchmarking of relevant biosecurity measures will be disseminated and visual material and guidance as support for farming schools and working farmers will be provided. In addition, project findings will be provided as multi-lingual and “easy-to-apply” web-content. A support tool for the calculation of cost effectiveness of preventive biosecurity measures will be developed that assists farmers, risk managers and other stakeholders. Finally, a workshop series will be organised to connect researchers and stakeholders in a farm-to-fork fashion to discuss and rate specific biosecurity measures and inform attendees about project results.